

What sociodemographic and work characteristics are associated with musculoskeletal complaints in nursing students? A cross-sectional analysis of repeated measurements

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ABSTRACT

Musculoskeletal complaints (MSCs) arise during nursing education. We examined cross-sectional associations between self-reported MSCs and both sociodemographic and workplace characteristics in different clinical placement settings. We included two observations among three cohorts of third-year Dutch nursing students (total N = 711) of the undergraduate nursing program of Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences. Questionnaire data on sociodemographic, physical and psychosocial work characteristics, and MSCs were used. Generalized estimating equation analysis for repeated measurements with backward elimination was used to examine associations with MSCs.

In total, 79% of students experienced MSCs. Female sex (OR 0.37, 95% CI 0.22–0.62), lifting and bending (OR 1.01, 95% CI 1.00–1.03), physical job demands (OR 2.33, 95% CI 1.68–3.22) and need for recovery (OR 1.02, 95% CI 1.01–1.03), were statistically significantly associated with overall MSCs. Models for regional complaints are also presented in this article. Nursing school and clinical placement staff should consider these factors when dealing with nursing students with MSCs.

1. Introduction

The demand for nurses is high, and the retention of nurses is a global challenge. The World Health Organisation (WHO) predicts increased global demand for health and social care staff by 2030, of which nurses comprise about half the global healthcare workforce (World Health Organisation, 2016). The decision to leave the nursing profession is the result of a complex process (Kox et al., 2020a), in which physical health characteristics might play a role. Musculoskeletal complaints affect the work ability of nurses (Ou et al., 2021) and may contribute to leaving the profession (Fochsen et al., 2006; Gilchrist and Pokorná, 2021).

Addressing this problem early and ongoing, preferably starting during nursing education, may contribute to the long-term retention of nurses.

2. Background

Musculoskeletal complaints (MSCs) give rise to work disability (Hartvigsen et al., 2018), absenteeism (Alexopoulos et al., 2011), and dropout from the nursing profession (Aiken et al., 2001). Aiken's study (Aiken et al., 2001) among 43,000 nurses in 5 countries, reported 17%–39% having the intention to leave their profession within the next year due to physical and psychological job demands. Fochsen et al. (2006)

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showed that 26% of nurses employed in hospitals in Sweden were no longer employed in nursing care a decade later. MSCs of the neck/shoulder or knees as well as physical working conditions were among the variables that were associated with their leaving nursing care. US nurses with high physically demanding jobs more often reported an intent to leave their position (Han et al., 2015). Given the current shortage of nurses and the growing demand for nursing professionals in the coming years (Haddad et al., 2020), these findings are worrying.

Nurses are often exposed to physically demanding tasks, such as lifting, bending, working in awkward positions and repetitiveness in nursing tasks. This may result in overexertion injuries to nurses' musculoskeletal system (Trinkoff et al., 2003). MSCs are common in the nursing profession (Heiden et al., 2013; Westergren et al., 2019; Ellapen and Narsigan, 2014; Soylar and Ozer, 2018), with prevalence rates for low back pain of 40–88% (Tosunoz and Oztunc, 2017), and for neck-shoulder-arm pain 13–96% (Long et al., 2013). Prevalence rates of MSCs in the lower extremities range between 3.2% and 100% (Stoit et al., 2016). Different settings and clinical situations, and different instruments and scales, may partly account for the varying prevalence rates. The annual prevalence of low back pain in Nigerian nurses was 73.5% (Sikiru and Hanifa, 2010) and the low back pain prevalence in Turkish nurses was 49.7% (Pinar, 2010).

The development of MSCs starts already among nursing students during their clinical placements (Cheung, 2010; Smith and Leggat, 2004). Two studies reported that MSCs were most common in the spine area (neck, upper back, and lower back) among nursing students in Sweden (Lövgren et al., 2014), with a prevalence rate of 51% for neck pain, and Turkey (Buyukavci et al., 2020) with a 12-month prevalence rate of 33.5% for neck pain.

A high incidence of MSCs has been identified in novice nurses. 39% of nurses in the first four years of their working career reported MSCs (Vendittelli et al., 2016). Mitchell et al. (2008) indicated that MSCs were more prevalent during the last two years of nursing training and over the period from student to working nurse than at the start of the nursing education. They suggested that increased occupational exposure and more frequent and intensive physical work demands contribute to this. Effective interventions for preventing work related MSCs for nursing students and novice nurses are scarce (Kox et al., 2020b). It is therefore imperative to provide appropriate support during and shortly after nursing education (Lövgren et al., 2014) to avoid increasing MSCs.

It is unclear what sociodemographic and workplace characteristics contribute to MSCs in nursing students. This study explored possible cross-sectional associations between these characteristics, and self-reported MSCs.

3. Methods

3.1. Study design

A cross-sectional analysis of repeated measurements.

3.2. Setting

The Bachelor of Nursing degree program of Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences has a yearly average of 500 first-year students (Vereniging Hogescholen, 2020). This four-year accredited educational program includes four clinical placements of 20 weeks each (80 weeks in total): one clinical placement in year 2 (first or second semester), two clinical placements in year 3, and one clinical placement in year 4 (second semester).

3.3. Study population

All third-year nursing students of three consecutive academic years (from 2015–2016 to 2017–2018) of the undergraduate nursing program of Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences (N = 995) were invited to

participate. Prior to being invited to participate in the study, students received oral and written information about the study, with presentations and flyers.

3.4. Data collection

Online self-administered questionnaires were sent by e-mail in the twelfth week of the second semester of the third study year (second placement setting of year 3). One year later, in the second semester of the fourth year, an identical follow-up questionnaire was sent, except that the first questionnaire contained questions on sociodemographic data such as gender and ethnicity. The questionnaires addressed the outcome variable, that is, MSCs during the current clinical placement, and a number of potential associated factors that were derived from the literature and the researchers' expertise.

The students could complete the questionnaires as part of the educational program during lectures. Up to three follow-up invitations to participate in the study were sent. Participants did not receive compensation for their participation.

3.5. Outcome variable

The outcome of interest for the current study was MSCs during the students' current clinical placement. MSCs were assessed using the Dutch Musculoskeletal Questionnaire (DMQ) (Hildebrandt, 2001), including questions about having musculoskeletal ache, pain, or discomfort in each of twelve body regions supported by a body map

Complaints of neck, back and limbs
During your current clinical placement, do you have pain, discomfort of your:

	Yes, long term	Yes, regularly	Yes, once in a while	No, never
neck	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
shoulders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
upper back	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
upper arm	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
lower back	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
elbows	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
wrists / hands	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
pelvis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
thighs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
knees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
lower legs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ankles / feet	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Fig. 1. Body map diagram.

diagram (Fig. 1).

The twelve body regions were combined into three anatomical areas according to the 'Multidisciplinary guideline non-specific Complaints Arm, Neck and/or Shoulders' (Beumer et al., 2012), 'JGZ guideline Extremities, including thighs, knees, lower legs and ankles/feet' (Deurloo and Lanting, 2019), and 'KNGF practice guideline 'Low back pain' (Staal et al., 2017): 1) upper extremities (hands/wrists, elbows, upper arm, neck, shoulders and upper back); 2) lower back area (lower back and pelvis); and 3) lower extremities (thighs, knees, lower legs and ankles/feet).

MSC variables were modelled as dichotomous variables per anatomical area; 'MSCs' (including 'yes, long-lasting' or 'yes, regularly') and 'no MSCs' (including 'yes, once in a while' or 'no, never').

3.6. Sociodemographic characteristics

The following sociodemographic factors were used: sex, age, body mass index (BMI), living situation, ethnicity, prior education, and study route. Living situation was modelled dichotomously: living with parents or not living with parents. Ethnicity was modelled dichotomously: Dutch or western migration background, or non-western migration background. Students were classified as having a non-western migration background, when at least one parent was born in a non-western country (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (CBS), 2020). Prior education was classified into three levels: 1) higher general secondary or pre-university education, 2) academic higher education or 3) vocational education and training, in-service training, or other. Study route was classified into: 1) full-time, 2) part-time, or 3) combined study-work programme.

3.7. Physical workplace characteristics

The following physical workplace factors were included: lifting and bending, physical job demands, Visual Display Unit work (VDU), the number of colleagues that the student works with on an average working day, the daily number of patients cared for, current clinical placement setting, and physical activity level. The 8-item 'lifting and bending' scale from the NEXT questionnaire (Kuemmerling et al., 2003) was used to assess exposure to lifting and bending, with a possible range from 0 to 100 (the higher the score, the higher the exposure to lifting and bending). Physical job demands were measured with subscales of the Job Content Questionnaire (JCQ) (Karasek et al., 1998). Visual Display Unit work was assessed with two questions from the Dutch Questionnaire on the Experience and Evaluation of Work (VBBA) (Van Veldhoven and Meijman, 1994), on the frequency (no-little/often-always) and duration (mean number of hours per day). The daily number of colleagues working with was modelled into '0 to 1' and '2 or more'. Current clinical placement settings were modelled using five categories: 1) hospital care, 2) nursing home care, 3) home care, 4) mental health care, and 5) other (including care for disabled, youth healthcare, other settings).

3.8. Psychosocial workplace characteristics

We used the following subscales of the Job Content Questionnaire (JCQ) (Karasek et al., 1998): decision latitude (composed of decision authority and skill discretion), psychological job demands, and supervisor and co-worker social support to assess psychosocial work characteristics. For each subscale, a sum score was calculated, ranging from 1 to 4.

3.9. Physical and mental health characteristics

The Short Questionnaire to Assess Health-enhancing Physical Activity (SQUASH) was used to assess physical activity level; providing an indication of the number of days per week with at least 30 min of moderate physical activity (Wendel-Vos et al., 2003).

To measure distress, the generic 3-item Distress Screener (Braam et al., 2009) was used, with questions about suffering from worry or listlessness, and feeling tense during the past week. Distress was modelled dichotomously: no/yes. The 11-item need for recovery subscale (NFR) was used from the Dutch Questionnaire on the Experience and Evaluation of Work (Van Veldhoven and Broersen, 2003). A sum score was calculated, ranging from 0 to 100. Higher scores indicate a higher need for recovery.

3.10. Data analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis were applied to describe factors and outcome variables, using mean scores, standard deviations (SD), median and interquartile Range (IQR) for continuous variables, and frequency and percentages for categorical variables.

Before running our model, (multi)collinearity was checked to detect correlations between all factors. We did a nonparametric correlation test, applying Spearman's rho (with cut-off > 0.7). For factors showing (multi)collinearity, the factor with the strongest association to the primary outcome was selected for the model; for the current study, 'BMI' was kept over 'weight'. After removal of weight, the models were no longer subject to multicollinearity issues.

Cross-sectional associations between sociodemographic, workplace and health characteristics, and MSCs were evaluated using Generalized Estimating Equation (GEE). GEE is an appropriate method for analyzing cross-sectional associations with repeated measures. In the current study, GEE accounts for changes in clinical placement setting and personal circumstances over time (that is, between the two observations in the third and fourth academic year) within individual students.

We constructed four models through backward elimination ($p > 0.05$ for removal), for each anatomical area (upper extremities, lower back, and lower extremities) and for total MSCs. The significance level for inclusion of a factor in our final model was set at p-value 0.05. All variables included in the model were measured at the two observations, except for sex, age, country of birth, ethnicity, first language, study route, prior education, and height. Odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals for each factor were calculated. All analyses were performed in IBM SPSS version 26.0. All analyses were performed in IBM SPSS version 26.0.

3.11. Ethical considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Medical Ethical Review Committee of the Erasmus University Medical Center Rotterdam (MEC number: FMS/sl/273789). The research was carried out in accordance with the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice of the Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU). All participants received oral and written information about the study and gave written informed consent.

4. Results

4.1. Participants' characteristics

In total, 711 of 995 eligible nursing students (71.4%) participated in this study. 115 other students did not respond to the invitation and 169 did not give permission to use their data. Of about half of this group (359; 50.5%), we also received a second measurement. For three of these students, only the first of the two observations was used in the model, because of missing data (they did no clinical placement at the second observation). This left us with a total of 1067 observations.

The mean age of participants was 23.5 (SD 5.5 years). Most participants were female (90.2%). The sociodemographic and workplace characteristics (year 3) of the individuals are shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Demographic, physical and psychosocial work and health characteristics (N=711).

	N (%) unless specified otherwise
Sample size, N	711
Sociodemographic characteristics	
Sex (% female)	641 (90.2%)
Age (years), mean ± SD (range)	23.50 ± 5.46 (19 to 55)
Median; IQR	22; 4
Height (cm), mean ± SD (range)	170.37 ± 8.26 (146 to 200)
Median; IQR	170; 10
BMI (kg/m ²), mean ± SD (range)	23.71 ± 4.18 (15.6 to 67.6)
Median; IQR	23.03; 4.45
Living situation (% with parents)	400 (56.3%)
Ethnicity (% Dutch or western migration background)	498 (70%)
Dutch as first language (% Dutch)	614 (86.4%)
Country of birth (% the Netherlands)	639 (89.9%)
Prior education	
•Higher general secondary education	393 (55.3%)
•Pre-university education & academic higher education	106 (14.9%)
•Intermediate vocational education and training & in-service training & other	212 (29.8%)
Study route	
•fulltime programme	439 (61.7%)
•work-study programme	212 (29.8%)
•part-time study programme	60 (8.4%)
Current clinical placement	
•hospital	338 (47.5%)
•elderly care	81 (11.4%)
•home care	189 (26.6%)
•mental healthcare	55 (7.7%)
•other	48 (6.8%)
Physical workplace characteristics ^a	
Lifting and bending, mean ± SD (range)	26.48 ± 18.72 (0 to 100)
Median; IQR	22.1; 25.0
Physical job demands, mean ± SD (range)	2.65 ± 0.60 (1 to 4)
Median; IQR	2.75; 0.75
Total time spent on VDU work, mean ± SD (range)	3.78 ± 2.67 (0 to 24)
Median; IQR	3.0; 3
VDU work (% often/always)	552 (77.6%)
Daily number of colleagues working with:	
•0 or 1	169 (23.8%)
•2 or more	542 (76.2%)
Daily number of patients cared for, mean ± SD (range)	7.65 ± 5.43 (1 to 80)
Median; IQR	6.0; 6
Psychosocial workplace characteristics ^b	
Decision latitude, mean ± SD (range)	2.95 ± 0.41 (1 to 3.92)
Median; IQR	2.92; 0.50
Psychological job demands, mean ± SD (range)	2.85 ± 0.50 (1-4)
Median; IQR	2.83; 0.75
Supervisor support, mean ± SD (range)	2.94 ± 0.62 (1 to 4)
Median; IQR	3.0; 0.50
Co-worker support, mean ± SD (range)	3.09 ± 0.48 (1.5 to 4)
Median; IQR	3.0; 0.50
Physical and mental health characteristics	
Distress (% moderate to high distress)	324 (45.6%)
Need for recovery (0-100), mean ± SD (range)	63.37 ± 27.07 (0 to 100)
Median; IQR	72.73; 36.36
Total activity score (SQUASH) ^c , mean ± SD (range)	7,984.5 ± 5,033.6 (0 to 39,060)
Median; IQR	6,900; 6,075
Musculoskeletal complaints during current clinical placement ^d	
Overall MSC at any body part (% regular /long-lasting)	558 (78.5%)

Table 1 (continued)

	N (%) unless specified otherwise
Complaints of the upper extremities area (% regular /long-lasting)	405 (57.0%)
Complaints of the lower back area (% regular /long-lasting)	399 (56.1%)
Complaints of lower extremities (% regular /long-lasting)	293 (41.2%)

Body mass index (BMI); Inter Quartile Range (IQR); Short QUESTIONNAIRE to ASSESS Health-enhancing physical activity (SQUASH).

^a The potential range of total scores was 0 to 100 for lifting and bending; and 1 to 4 to the subscale Physical Job Demands of the Job Content Questionnaire.

^b The potential range of total scores was 1 to 4 to the subscales Decision Latitude, Psychological Job Demands, Supervisor Support and Collegial Support of the Job Content Questionnaire.

^c SQUASH-score: the total activity score is the product of the total time (in minutes) and the intensity of activities per week.

^d Of the 558 students having any MSC, 555 (99.5%) indicated that the MSC was partly or completely related to their clinical placement or work.

4.2. Musculoskeletal complaints

The overall prevalence of regular or long-lasting MSCs in any body part among nursing students at the first observation was high (79%). The majority (99.5%) indicated that these complaints were clinical placement related. Of the students at the first observation, 57% had regular or long-lasting MSCs of the upper extremities. For the lower back and the lower extremities, these percentages were 56% and 41%, respectively. Appendix A shows the indicated MSCs per body part at the first measurement (N = 711) and at the second measurement (N = 359).

4.3. Sociodemographic and workplace characteristics

Using backward elimination to improve our models, the following factors were removed from all four models: Age, height, working at a screen, average number of hours of screenwork, supervisor support, co-worker support, total activity score (SQUASH), number of colleagues, living situation.

The full list of multivariate associations between MSCs by anatomical area and the various characteristics in the four final models is presented in Appendices B, C, D and E. Based on the 1067 observations of 711 participants, we could determine three statistically significant associated factors that recurred in all anatomical areas of MSCs (male sex, physical job demands, need for recovery; see Table 2). Two other associated factors (lifting and bending and study route) recurred in three anatomical areas.

5. Discussion

Already in the third year of nursing education, we found high prevalence's of MSCs (overall 79%; neck-shoulder-upper extremity 57%; low back and pelvis 56%; lower extremities 41%) in nursing students. About four out of five nursing students of our cohort experienced regular or long-lasting MSCs (pain or discomfort). Studies of MSCs among nursing students are scarce, but high overall MSC prevalence rates were also found in Turkish nursing students (73.2%) and Swedish novice nurses (50%) (Lövgren et al., 2014; Buyukavci et al., 2020).

Several factors in different domains were associated with MSCs. First, exposure to physical work conditions, such as lifting and bending activities and other physical job demands, were associated with higher proportions of MSCs. This is in line with existing evidence from studies among (registered) nurses (Ellapen and Narsigan, 2014).

Secondly, we found an association between MSCs and several psychosocial work characteristics. Students who had few control options during clinical placements (low decision latitude) more often reported complaints in the upper extremities. Decision control was found to be

Table 2
Determinants associated with MSCs in nursing students (1067 observations).^a

Determinants	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
	Overall MSC		Upper extremities		Low back		Lower extremities	
	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI	OR	95% CI
Sex (reference: female)	0.37***	0.22 - 0.62	0.55*	0.33 - 0.91	0.57*	0.35 - 0.93	0.28***	0.16 - 0.51
Need for recovery (0 to 100)	1.02***	1.01 - 1.03	1.01***	1.01 - 1.02	1.02***	1.01 - 1.02	1.01***	1.01 - 1.02
Physical job demands (1 to 4)	2.33***	1.68 - 3.22	2.49***	1.89 - 3.28	2.03***	1.56 - 2.64	1.69***	1.31 - 2.19
Lifting and bending (0 to 100)	1.01**	1.00 - 1.03			1.01*	1.00 - 1.02	1.01*	1.00 - 1.02
Study route: part-time (reference: full-time)			1.80*	0.95 - 3.41			0.53*	0.32 - 0.88
BMI (15 to 68)							1.06**	1.02 - 1.09
Distress (reference: no distress)			1.60***	1.21 - 2.11				
Decision latitude (1 to 4)			0.67*	0.47 - 0.95				
Prior education: secondary vocational nursing education (reference: senior general secondary education)			1.43*	1.01 - 2.03				
Psychological job demands (1 to 4)			0.71*	0.52 - 0.96				
Clinical placement setting: nursing homes and elderly care (reference: hospital)			0.60*	0.39 - 0.91				
Ethnicity (reference: non-Western background)					0.62**	0.46 - 0.84		
Daily number of patients cared for (1 to 80)							0.96**	0.94 - 0.99
First language (reference: Dutch)							2.03***	1.34 - 3.08

OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval

*p ≤ 0.05, **p ≤ 0.01, ***p ≤ 0.001.

^a For categorical factors, the odds ratios are computed with respect to the specified reference category; for continuous factors, the odds ratios are computed per unit increase. Cells are left empty if that factor was not included in the final model.

associated with MSCs for shoulder pain (Herin et al., 2012) and complaints in the wrists/hands and the upper spine (Bugajska et al., 2013), in a general working population. Decision latitude was also associated with neck, shoulder and lower back pain among female employees in human services (Larsman and Hanse, 2009). Low decision latitude may contribute to job strain, which in turn is a risk factor of musculoskeletal pain and other health complaints (Vegchel, 2005; Amiri and Behnezhad, 2020).

Thirdly, we found an association between MSCs and some physical and mental health related characteristics of the nursing students; need for recovery, distress, and BMI. Students with increased need for recovery reported more MSCs. An association between need for recovery and MSCs was also found in other studies among other professions (Park et al., 2021; Sluiter, 1999; Gawke et al., 2012; Moriguchi et al., 2012; Alexopoulos et al., 2006). It remains unclear, however, whether insufficient recovery time leads to MSCs, or whether having MSCs increases the need for recovery.

Students who experienced distress, had more complaints in the upper extremities. This finding is consistent with previous studies (Hauke et al., 2011; Amin et al., 2018). In their meta-analysis on the impact of work-related psychosocial stressors on the onset of MSCs, Hauke et al. (2011) found the largest estimate for effect size for psychological distress and the upper extremities. Amin et al. (2018) found that nurses with higher emotional distress had more MSCs, with the highest OR reported in the upper extremities.

An increasing BMI is significantly associated with MSCs of the lower extremity. This is consistent with various other studies (Lin et al., 2020; Stolt et al., 2016; Tukker et al., 2009); there is a strong association between overweight/obesity and complaints of the lower extremities (Lin et al., 2020; Tukker et al., 2009; Kulkarni et al., 2016).

Somewhat unexpectedly, clinical placements in the nursing home

setting were negatively associated with MSCs of the upper extremities. Perhaps, this can be explained by the availability and higher use of patient handling equipment (Koppelaar et al., 2011) or collegial assistance with a lift.

For some of the associated factors, we do not have a sound explanation. Intermediate vocational degree trained nursing students and part-time course route students have in common that they often have a (part-time) nursing job besides their bachelor nursing training. Perhaps these students have to support themselves or their families financially and experience more distress and/or other stressors that cause low back and upper extremities complaints.

Finally, a higher daily number of patients cared for was slightly, but negatively associated with lower limb complaints. In general, the number of patients a student must care for has little influence on the development of complaints of the lower extremities. Contrary to our finding, Larese & Fiorio (Larese and Fiorito, 1994) found that nurses working in wards with high patient to nurse ratios had more MSCs than those working in wards with lower ratios. Satisfactory ratios between nurses and patients could improve work efficiency and decrease injury rates (Larese and Fiorito, 1994).

5.1. Methodological considerations

This study examined possible cross-sectional associations between sociodemographic, workplace and health characteristics, and self-reported MSCs in nursing students, using a total of 1067 observations.

We dichotomized the outcome measure of our study, because of our specific interest in the more severe MSCs, as these, in particular, are associated with care-seeking and absenteeism. In addition, we classified the MSCs into three gross anatomical areas, in line with current guidelines (Beumer et al., 2012; Deurloo and Lanting, 2019; Staal et al.,

2017). Consequently, we did not obtain insight into the associated factors of MSCs in specific body parts. For a more thorough exploration of associated factors of MSCs in the specific body parts, it would be relevant to also include some more complaint-specific ergonomic risk factors.

The use of self-reported measurements of physical exposure limits the ability to draw specific conclusions. For example, it is possible that the actual incidence of MSCs may have been over- or underestimated. Though we used validated instruments, we would have preferred more objective measures of physical exposure in the field, such as Accelerometry, Actigraph or Pedometer. This was, however, deemed impractical, time-consuming and too costly.

Included psychosocial work and health characteristics that may increase MSCs, were limited to the Job Content Questionnaire (JCQ) scales assessing decision latitude, psychological job demands, supervisor and co-worker support (Karasek et al., 1998); distress (Braam et al., 2009); and NFR scale (Van Veldhoven and Broersen, 2003). The validity of these instruments has not been investigated for the group of nursing students doing a clinical placement. This offers opportunities for further research. These instruments, however, have been used in other studies among registered nurses and other student groups.

Another limitation of our study is that the results might not be fully generalized, because the students who participated in our study may have been healthier and less prone to dropout than the students who did not participate (volunteer bias). This might mean that some of the associations in our final model may have been underestimated and would have been stronger if the non-participating students could have been included in our study.

Having a second measurement for a substantial part of the students should be seen as a strength of our study. This allowed to examine the association between the factors and MSCs while taking the changes over time within individuals into account.

5.2. Recommendations for practice and future research

Because of the high prevalence of MSCs, associated factors contributing to MSCs in nursing students should be considered by nursing education providers and clinical placement providers. First, it is important that they make an effort to lower physical job demands and invest in proper training and aids that contribute to the prevention and decrease of MSCs in nursing students.

Second, stress management programs may help reducing nursing students' stress. Preferably, such programs should focus on both the individual's coping strategies and psychosocial workplace stressors (Galbraith and Brown, 2011).

Third, nursing students with a high BMI could benefit from weight loss. Weight loss has been shown to significantly improve knee pain and function among overweight and obese individuals (Woolf et al., 2008).

The interplay between job stressors, need for recovery and MSCs in nursing students is complex. To understand this fully, further research is needed. Furthermore, other factors that were not included in our study may further explain MSCs in nursing students.

6. Conclusion

The prevalence of MSCs is high among nursing students. This study provided insights in sociodemographic and physical and psychosocial workplace characteristics that are associated with MSCs among these nursing students. Sociodemographic factors were being female, non-Dutch first language and non-Western ethnicity, part-time study route, increasing BMI, and prior secondary vocational nursing education. Workplace related factors were high physical job demands, lifting and bending, higher daily number of patients cared for, low decision latitude, and low psychological job demands. A clinical placement in the nursing home setting was related to a smaller odds of MSCs of the upper extremities. Relevant health variables were higher need for recovery and distress. Nursing school and clinical placement staff should consider these factors when dealing with nursing students with MSCs.

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Author contributions

PR and HM initiated and designed the study. JK and EB performed the data collection. Formal data analysis was done by JK, under supervision of JR, HG and PR. Data outcome was discussed with JK, JR, HG, PR and SBZ. JK produced the first draft of the manuscript with guidance from JR, HG, PR and SBZ. All authors (JK, JR, HG, SBZ, EB, HM and PR) contributed substantially to the manuscript and critically revised the content. All authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. MSCs per bodypart at first (T0) (N = 711) and at second (T1) (N = 359) measurement

T0 (N = 711): Complaints of:	Yes, long term N (%)	Yes, regularly N (%)	Yes, once in a while N (%)	No, never N (%)
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T0 (N = 711): Complaints of:	Yes, long term N (%)	Yes, regularly N (%)	Yes, once in a while N (%)	No, never N (%)
Neck	75 (10.5)	183 (25.7)	230 (32.3)	223 (31.4)
Shoulders	74 (10.4)	193 (27.1)	225 (31.6)	219 (30.8)
Upper back	72 (10.1)	170 (23.9)	174 (24.5)	295 (41.5)
Upper arms	7 (1)	32 (4.5)	97 (13.6)	575 (80.9)
Elbows	1 (0.1)	17 (2.4)	39 (5.5)	654 (92.0)
Wrists/hands	23 (3.2)	70 (9.8)	126 (17.7)	492 (69.2)
Lower back	118 (16.6)	272 (38.3)	190 (26.7)	131 (18.4)
Hips	15 (2.1)	47 (6.6)	96 (13.5)	553 (77.8)
Thigh bone	5 (0.7)	28 (3.9)	47 (6.6)	631 (88.7)
Knees	41 (5.8)	110 (15.5)	165 (23.2)	395 (55.6)
Lower legs	13 (1.8)	73 (10.3)	90 (12.7)	535 (75.2)
Ankles/feet	42 (5.9)	167 (23.5)	209 (29.4)	293 (41.2)
T1 (N = 359) Complaints of:	Yes, long term N (%)	Yes, regularly N (%)	Yes, once in a while N (%)	No, never N (%)
Neck	29 (8.1)	102 (28.4)	116 (32.3)	112 (31.2)
Shoulders	32 (8.9)	93 (25.9)	123 (34.3)	111 (30.9)
Upper back	34 (9.5)	67 (18.7)	100 (27.9)	158 (44.0)
Upper arms	5 (1.4)	14 (3.9)	54 (15.0)	286 (79.7)
Elbows	2 (0.6)	6 (1.7)	17 (4.7)	334 (93.0)
Wrists/hands	13 (3.3)	32 (8.9)	78 (21.7)	237 (66.0)
Lower back	55 (15.3)	138 (38.4)	102 (28.4)	64 (17.8)
Hips	11 (3.1)	20 (5.6)	58 (16.2)	270 (75.2)
Thigh bone	0 (0.0)	10 (2.8)	23 (6.4)	326 (90.8)
Knees	16 (4.5)	63 (17.5)	78 (21.7)	202 (56.3)
Lower legs	5 (1.4)	31 (8.6)	52 (14.5)	271 (75.5)
Ankles/feet	22 (6.1)	66 (18.4)	94 (26.2)	177 (49.3)

Appendix B. Factors associated with all MSCs in nursing students (1067 observations)

Overall complaints	p	OR	95% CI
Sex (reference: female)	0.000	0.370	0.222–0.617
Lifting and bending (0–100)	0.021	1.013	1.002–1.025
Physical job demands (1–4)	0.000	2.327	1.680–3.224
Need for recovery (0–100)	0.000	1.018	1.012–1.025

p = p-value; OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval.

Appendix C. Factors associated with complaints of the upper extremities in nursing students (1067 observations)

Complaints of the upper extremities	p	OR	95% CI
Sex (reference: female)	0.021	0.550	0.331–0.913
Prior education: secondary vocational nursing education (reference: senior general secondary education)	0.044	1.430	1.009–2.027
Study route (reference: full-time)	0.072	1.799	0.948–3.412
Clinical placement setting: nursing homes and elderly care (reference: hospital)	0.017	0.595	0.338–0.913
Physical job demands (1–4)	0.000	2.487	1.885–3.280
Psychological job demands (1–4)	0.025	0.707	0.522–0.958
Distress (reference: no distress)	0.001	1.595	1.208–2.106
Decision Latitude (1–4)	0.026	0.673	0.474–0.954
Need for recovery (0–100)	0.000	1.014	1.008–1.019

p = p-value; OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval.

Appendix D. Factors associated with low back complaints in nursing students (1067 observations)

Low back complaints	p	OR	95% CI
Sex (reference: female)	0.024	0.570	0.350–0.929
Ethnicity (reference: non-Western background)	0.002	0.620	0.456–0.842
Lifting and bending (0–100)	0.049	1.008	1.000–1.017
Physical job demands (1–4)	0.000	2.027	1.560–2.635
Need for recovery (0–100)	0.000	1.015	1.010–1.021

p = p-value; OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval.

Appendix E. Factors associated with complaints of the lower extremities in nursing students (1067 observations)

Complaints of the lower extremities	p	OR	95% CI
Sex (reference: female)	0,000	0,281	0,155–0,508
Study route (reference: full-time)	0,015	0,530	0,319–0,883
BMI (15–68)	0,003	1,055	1,018–1,092
Lifting and bending (0–100)	0,030	1,010	1,001–1,018
Daily number of patients cared for (1–80)	0,007	0,962	0,935–0,989
Physical job demands (1–4)	0,000	1,694	1,309–2,192
Need for recovery (0–100)	0,000	1,014	1,008–1,019
Dutch as first language (reference: Dutch)	0,001	2,031	1,337–3,084

p = p-value; OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval.

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